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“Biochemistry in Biotechnology”

Foreword

Dear colleagues

Welcome to the XII Conference of The Serbian Biochemical Society, entitled 'Biochemistry in Biotechnology'.

This year we have the richest program ever. In addition to our tradition to invite promising young researchers from four main university centers in Serbia to deliver lectures, we have eight guests from abroad that will participate through FEBS3+ program or within ANSO PRESSION project. This is a turning point in the organization of the conference which undergoes a transformation into scientific event with strong international character.

As always, we cherish the participation of PhD students and early career researchers. We are glad that many colleagues took the opportunity to show what they do and to find their place within the scientific ecosystem.

Organizing Committee

Biological activity of Serbian orange wines: polyphenolic content and inhibition of oxidative stress

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In the past ten years orange wines have significantly attracted the attention of wine producers, someliers and consumers. Orange wine is essentially white wine that is produced similarly to red wines, with long skin-contact fermentation, without any chemical or specific yeast. The phenolic profile and biological activity of orange wines have been poorly investigated¹. The aim of this study was to compare the polyphenolic profile (HPLC analysis), content of total polyphenols, flavonoids and tannins (spectrophotometric methods) in 24 orange wines from Serbia and to evaluate their potential to inhibit oxidative stress in *in vitro* cell-based model (human monocytes, U937 cell line). The oxidative stress in U937 cells was induced by 2,2'-azobis(2-amidinopropane)dihydrochloride, while dichlorofluorescein diacetate was used to monitor intracellular level of oxidative stress. Among the examined polyphenolics, catechin (0–76.7 mg/L), followed by gallic (0–49.5 mg/L) and caffeic acid (0–22.2 mg/L) were dominant polyphenols in examined wines, while sporadic occurrence of some anthocyanins was noticed. All wines had significant amounts of total polyphenols (227.0–1318 µg gallic acid equivalent/mL of wine), flavonoids (33.55–104.9 µg quercetin equivalent/mL of wine) and tannins (145.8–1254 µg catechin equivalent/mL of wine). Regarding inhibition of oxidative stress, the activity range varied from 138.0 to 1063 µg trolox equivalent/mL of wine, implicating that examined wine samples are effective inhibitors of oxidative stress.

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References

1. Bene Z, Kallay M. Polyphenol contents of skin-contact fermented white wines. *Acta Alimentaria* 2019;48:515–24.